

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Asymptotic Freedom

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of coupling constants and in particular their rule as net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one, it is possible to reason for confinement and asymptotic freedom in rather simple and elegant way. High energy is synonymous with rolling quarks uphill in and endless hyperbole. They are destined to reach the minima of the hyperbole and cannot escape.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is wrapped in an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvature and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

Bosons were proven discrete amount of net curvature on the matrix tensor, we can represent them by the term in equation (1.3):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0; M \rightarrow \infty \quad (1.3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \in (+1) \cup \mathbb{P}$$

$$\mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

Supported by the coupling constant primorial series, in equations (2.1) to (2.13).

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2.1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.11)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2.12)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \quad (2.13)$$

Now, we have used the visualization of the sea of gluons on the Quark triplet in the following way.

In the context of asymptotic freedom, when we indulge in high energy collisions, that is synonymous with trying to roll the quark triplet uphill. It is possible to try as the bosons are just net curvature unbound as given by (1), however since each boson is a curvature of certain magnitude it increase the probability of arrival to its position, therefore we have a "sea" of gluons. For example, in the third coupling term presented in equations (3) to (3.1):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (3.1)$$

Taken from that point of analysis, asymptotic freedom is a result of curvature converging to a point, or the existence of gluons on the quark triplet. If the number of bosons is ever increasing on the quark triplet, so does the overall curvature of the magnitude. To roll a quark uphill an infinite curve is at the verge of impossible. The attempt to roll the quark triplet elements uphill will eventually lead to a the quark reaching the minima, lowest point on the curve. Similar to other physical phenomena aspiring minima. Overall the 8T from birds eye overview, allow us to explain phenomena which is considered "advanced" such as Pauli Principle, asymptotic freedom, Spin, the commuter, the reason for the coupling magnitudes, dark energy and probability of arrival in rather simple and elegant way. All we need is just two equations, (1) and the coupling constant series, divided to (2) and (2.1) to an additional element breaking the symmetry, the majestic three.

References

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